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Abstract: This article discusses the beneficial properties of the ginger plant. It contains information on medicinal products obtained from the ginger plant, their preparation, pharmaceutical effectiveness and elements.

Key words: essential oils, group B vitamins, enzymes, amino acids

Introduction. Ginger root and many have tasted it, but not everyone thought about what this plant looks like, where it grows and how it blooms. There are many types of ginger, but the usual thing that can be bought in almost every supermarket is significantly different from its decorative relatives, but its benefits are very high. Common ginger, or ginger, belongs to the ginger family, which has about 1,000 species in the pharmacy. This includes popular spices like turmeric and cardamom. The homeland of the plant is the north of India, from here the spices came to the market in medieval Europe. Later, the plant was cultivated in China, Japan, Australia, Indonesia, Thailand and other countries. The warm and humid tropics are considered a traditional comfortable habitat. Here it means evergreen perennial whose stem looks like a cane. The average plant reaches a height of 1-1.5 meters. Leaves narrow, lanceolate, stems strong, flowers inconspicuous, small to large torches. different colors. Wild life inside the herb can grow for decades, its root grows deep underground and every year it gives new shoots around the main and first specimen. It is easy to distinguish a young root crop from an old one by a very thin light skin, which you can only buy there.

The old root has a clear dark skin, very dense, it must be cut before eating. In plantations where the plant is grown for commercial purposes, it is considered an annual. In one season, which lasts 6-8 months, a complete plant with developed roots grows from a seed or plot. It is a young root that is highly valued and exported. The older the root, the more bitterness and less lung aroma. Ginger gets its name from the appearance of its most valuable part - the root. Translated from Sanskrit, "singabera" means horned or horn-shaped. It can reach 7 cm in length and 4 cm in width. Any ginger pulp contains a lot of coarse fibers. Separate black and white ginger. The first is the unprocessed, unpeeled root. The white color comes from the upper dense layer of the skin, which is thoroughly washed and dried. Inside, it can be a simple ginger light color with a slight yellow or green tint. there may be exotic species, pulp blue veins, the smell of kerosene and other unusual features. How Ginger Blooms-The common ginger, grown by many Europeans in plantations or in pots on windowsills, has a very simple appearance. If in favorable conditions it grows up to 1.5 meters and has large flowers, then it is grown on the windowsill, it is a leafy plant that resembles a shallower.

Lancet leaves, branching rhizome, small flowers and oblong seed capsule are the outward appearance. The flowers of ordinary ginger are not large. They look a little like an iris or an orchid in a lilac shade... There are large-flowered species on strong pedicels that protrude directly from the soil. These torches can have a red, lemon-colored, shaded transition. Different types of plants have highly decorative flowers, which at the same time have a pleasant smell. Ginger is one of the most valuable and mysterious plants with a rich history covered with many

legends. It is a versatile medicine, the hottest spice and an effective way to preserve beauty and youth. Now we know what it looks like and can grow it on our windowsill. Ginger is a spice, ornamental and medicinal plant at the same time. The largest number has a characteristic root. The full name is medicinal ginger. It grows naturally in the tropical region. In ginger, the leaves have a linear type and are arranged alternately on the stem. The underground part of plants is usually called a root, but it is a rhizome. It has several parts and looks like a hand.

Useful properties of ginger - The main concentration of nutrients is located in the root of the plant. The root grows to the maximum until autumn. Harvesting is done after the plant has bloomed and all the leaves have fallen. Raw materials are cleaned from the ground and dried in the sun.

Below you can find out 7 useful properties of ginger.

Acid reflux can be caused by the food eaten or the person's anatomy. Some people are prone to it. Research shows that drinking or eating a special ginger tea every day can eliminate acid reflux. Inflammation is a defense mechanism when an injured or damaged part of the body needs to be isolated to limit damage to other areas. Nevertheless, the inflammatory process is painful and unpleasant. People suffering from chronic inflammatory diseases are especially effective in consuming ginger. Reduce the risk of cancer.

The effect of ginger on cancer cells is more active than the effect of other plants. Research shows that ginger kills cancer cells faster and more safely than chemotherapy drugs. As you know, chemotherapy can cause many health problems.

Ginger is also used to prevent inflammation of the colon and small intestine.

Get rid of digestive problems. Ginger can stop nausea. This is because ginger kills the harmful bacteria that cause ulcers. Ginger is also good for stimulating the salivary glands, which are an integral part of the digestive process. Get Rid of and Prevent Headaches Ginger's anti-inflammatory properties can also help treat headaches. Research shows that eating ginger every day can prevent headaches and even migraines.

Do you want to lose weight? Losing weight is a very difficult matter. An increase in fat reserves in the body is the main factor of many diseases. Diet plays a big role in weight loss, but obesity can also be caused by genes. Ginger also keeps the metabolism in the same level. Diet has a negative effect on metabolism. Don't Overcome Muscle Soreness Another common type of soreness is muscle soreness, which is often caused by exercise or daily routine. Research has shown that ginger helps in this case as well. However, the effect of ginger in this regard does not immediately relieve muscle pain, but gradually heals it. Eating ginger every day will prevent the pain that happens later in your body.

Ginger root is the main product of the plant. Infusions and tinctures are prepared on the basis of ginger, which are consumed internally and applied externally in the form of lotions and compresses. Medicines for cooking use raw and dried root. The benefits of ginger are in its rich composition. The root of the plant has analgesic, carminative, antispasmodic, bactericidal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, diaphoretic, choleric and tonic effects. The healing properties of ginger allow it to be used in traditional medicine recipes. The plant is useful for immunity. It has a tonic effect, restores strength after illness and prevents colds and flu. The dried root helps the production of gastric juice, normalizes the digestive process and eliminates spasms of any origin. The plant is often used in dietetics for weight loss. Ginger normalizes the cardiovascular system. It lowers cholesterol, strengthens blood vessels and cleans the blood. Ginger is used

topically to treat cuts, wounds, and burns. Funds based on it quickly relieve pain and prevent tissue infection.

In conclusion, there are contraindications to the use of ginger. We must act according to these instructions. Contraindications: Excessive consumption of ginger can harm the body. Nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea occur with excessive consumption of spices. Uncontrolled intake of plant products can cause an allergic reaction. Knowing how to use ginger properly is very useful.

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